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Australian
BioCommons

Proteomics Bioinformatics Infrastructure Roadmap for Australia

V4.0

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O. Johan R. Gustafsson and Jeffrey H. Christiansen

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1. Executive Summary

At its core, proteomics is a methods based discipline that seeks to characterise the proteome and its constituent proteins, and better understand their role in natural systems. Proteomics is considered here to include proteomics itself as well as aligned fields of peptidomics, structural proteomics, phosphoproteomics, glycoproteomics and meta-proteomics.

Many different questions can be addressed using proteomics, ranging from characterisation of key proteins, modifications, or structures or comparing the changes in proteome composition across species and environments and in response to the presence of an external stimulus, treatment, condition or pathology. In Australia, proteomics is conducted by researchers across medicine, agriculture and biodiversity.

This document includes:

- A summary of proteomics and its common methodologies;
- A review of how the Australian community currently undertakes this work and common data-, software- or compute-related infrastructure challenges faced by that community when using current approaches (information obtained through a survey, consultations with a 'Special Interest Group' (SIG) of researchers undertaking proteomics across Australia and the Australasian Core Facilities group); and
- A high level description of key components of a shared proteomics infrastructure for Australia, which, when implemented, would enable Australian researchers from a wide range of institutions to undertake proteomics analysis, who would otherwise be unable to do so because of the reported data-, software- or compute-related roadblocks.

D1. A shared platform for primary proteomics bioinformatics analyses to provide all Australian researchers with access to a shared platform with tools and workflows for common proteomics applications, underpinned by sufficient compute resources and easily connected to a variety of data storage locations and key datasets from public repositories.

D2. Interactive environments to enable secondary analyses, visualisation, and exploration of proteomics data, both raw and derived to make it easier for Australian researchers to perform relevant statistical analyses, visualisations and/or exploratory data analyses of proteomics community data.

D3. Systems to enable submission and retrieval of raw (primary) and derived (secondary) proteomics datasets to / from appropriate global repositories to make it easier for any Australian researcher to share data publicly, in accordance with best-practice open science guidelines.

D4. A proteomics-specific training program, developed in conjunction with the proteomics community to ensure that Australian researchers can effectively make use of their proteomics data on national infrastructure

D5. Alignment, adoption and contribution to global best-practice efforts to accelerate research outcomes, reduce duplication of effort, and collectively sustain proteomics bioinformatics approaches

Feedback on the proposed components outlined in this initial draft plan is now sought from the SIG and any other Australian proteomics researchers. Following engagement with other stakeholder groups (i.e. international entities operating infrastructure elsewhere and Australian research IT infrastructure partners), further iterations of this document will be produced with a final version of the plan scheduled for December 2022.

2. Background and Context

In Australia, investments to establish community-scale infrastructure to support bioinformatics-based research have materialised in various forms and scales over the last decade under a range of funding schemes¹. One significant supporter is Bioplatforms Australia², which aims to develop and support Australia's national bioinformatics infrastructure and is funded under the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS)³.

Since 2019, Bioplatforms Australia has supported the Australian BioCommons ("BioCommons"), which is an initiative focussed on establishing improved access to bioinformatics tools, methods, datasets, computational infrastructure, and training for Australia's molecular life scientists to underpin world-class science. The BioCommons is currently coordinating several national consultations with various communities of practice to gain input from life science researchers, bioinformaticians, and infrastructure providers to identify, configure, connect and support infrastructure to support bioinformatics-based research and resources that are relevant to these research communities.

In order to support Australian researchers who use mass spectrometry (MS)- based proteomics and metabolomics in their research with computational infrastructure, throughout 2020 and 2021 the BioCommons embarked on an engagement process with Australian-based metabolomics and proteomics 'core facilities'⁴. That activity resulted in more than 80 frequently used tools for metabolomics or proteomics data analysis being installed on the Galaxy Australia⁵ web-based computational analysis platform to support the work of those facilities (or users of those facilities) for both teaching⁶ and research. In late 2021, the BioCommons also hosted a session at the annual meeting of the Australasian Core Facilities (ACF) group⁷, which included a survey and breakout sessions to continue collecting the requirements of the mass spectrometry core facilities with respect to required infrastructure⁸.

In parallel, and in order to form a view of requirements from a wider spectrum of Australian researchers using proteomics and metabolomics data, in September 2020, the BioCommons also convened and surveyed a SIG for the field of MS. This group includes researchers who apply MS-based approaches in their research as well as staff based at MS core facilities. It was collectively agreed by the SIG at that time, that in order to focus subsequent work, that two distinct consultation communities should be formed - one for proteomics and one for

¹ Schneider M.V., Griffin P.C. *et al.* 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1093%2Fbib%2Fbbx071>

² [Bioplatforms Australia](https://www.bioplatforms.com/) <https://www.bioplatforms.com/>

³ [National Collaborative Infrastructure Strategy \(NCRIS\)](https://www.education.gov.au/national-collaborative-research-infrastructure-strategy-ncris)

<https://www.education.gov.au/national-collaborative-research-infrastructure-strategy-ncris>

⁴ Australian Proteome Analysis Facility (APAF), Monash Proteomics and Metabolomics Facility and UniSA Mass Spectrometry and Proteomics

⁵ [Galaxy Australia](https://usegalaxy.org.au/) <https://usegalaxy.org.au/>

⁶ [BioCommons News December 2021: Leveraging Galaxy Australia to teach proteomics](https://www.biocommons.org.au/news/galaxy-proteomics-training)

<https://www.biocommons.org.au/news/galaxy-proteomics-training>

⁷ [The 4th Australasian Core Facilities \(ACF\) meeting \(2021\)](https://www.eventbrite.com.au/e/the-fourth-australasian-core-facilities-meeting-tickets-185240267627?keep_tld=1)

https://www.eventbrite.com.au/e/the-fourth-australasian-core-facilities-meeting-tickets-185240267627?keep_tld=1

⁸ [ACF meeting BioCommons Session Summary \(2021\)](https://docs.google.com/document/d/10C4ZMewuBfgMeEZVuWLOUR0L_RihKFSOBQeipujY7zQ/edit#)

https://docs.google.com/document/d/10C4ZMewuBfgMeEZVuWLOUR0L_RihKFSOBQeipujY7zQ/edit#

metabolomics. The proteomics-focused outcomes of the survey and meetings are described in this document, which summarises and represents the current or expected infrastructure roadblocks and challenges described by members of the proteomics community in Australia, and identifies the potential broad features and requirements for shared, national infrastructure that could help address these challenges.

Community input is welcomed at all times, as is nomination of additional members of the SIG, by emailing communities@biocommons.org.au

Feedback on the proposed components outlined in this initial draft plan is now sought from the SIG and any other Australian researchers or their collaborators undertaking proteomics analyses. Following engagement with other stakeholder groups (i.e. international entities operating proteomics analysis infrastructure elsewhere and Australian research IT infrastructure partners), further iterations of this document will be produced with a final version of the plan scheduled for December 2022.

3. Proteomics - methods and community

3.1 What is proteomics and how is it done?

“Proteomics” is the analysis of *proteomes*, a term coined by Marc Wilkins (UNSW) in the mid 90s⁹. A proteome is the entire observable set of proteins in a given biological or natural system (e.g. tissue, fluid, environmental sample) under specific conditions and / or at a given time point¹⁰. It is also important to note that proteomics describes an entire domain of research, and we therefore use proteomics as a catchall for aligned research areas, including peptidomics¹¹, structural proteomics¹², phosphoproteomics¹³, glycoproteomics¹⁴ and meta-proteomics¹⁵.

Given the central role of proteins as effector molecules in biology, analysing a proteome can be used to:

- Map the composition and dynamics of systems that include, but are not limited to, tissues, fluids¹⁶ and the environment¹⁷;
- Understand how normal cellular function contrasts with specific pathologies (e.g. cancer, infection, life-style diseases), to identify the presence of disease and its mechanisms¹⁸, and;

⁹ Wasinger VC. *et al.* 1995, <https://doi.org/10.1002/elps.11501601185>

¹⁰ Noor Z., Ahn S. B., *et al.* 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbz163>

¹¹ Foreman R.E. *et al.* 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jproteome.1c00295>

¹² Serpa J.J. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1255/ejms.1178>

¹³ Savage S.R and Zhang B. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12014-020-09290-x>

¹⁴ Chernykh A. *et al.* 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1042/BST20200222>

¹⁵ Lohmann P. *et al.* 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14789450.2020.1738931>

¹⁶ Omenn G.S. *et al.* 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jproteome.0c00485>

¹⁷ Lohmann P. *et al.* 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14789450.2020.1738931>

¹⁸ Doll S. *et al.* 2019, <https://dx.doi.org/10.1002%2Fprca.201800113>

- Measure the impact of cellular signalling or pharmaceutical intervention on a system¹⁹.

Characterising proteins at scale is a grand challenge. The Human Proteome Organisation (HuPO) illustrates this with an excellent timeline walkthrough of proteomics²⁰, from the invention of mass spectrometry in the early 1900s through to the proteomics “renaissance” in the 1990s and 2000s and most recently a 2020 metrics paper announcing credible evidence for more than 90% of the Human proteome²¹.

To put proteome analysis into perspective, there are more than 22,000 organism reference proteomes in the database UniProt (Universal Protein Resource)²² of which 1,703 have a protein count greater than 10,000. For *Homo sapiens* the reviewed protein count²³ is 20,405²⁴. Given the sheer number of ‘base’ proteins that a genome *may* express, and considering cell type expression patterns, protein concentration ranges, possible splice variants, post-translational modifications (PTMs, such as cleaving into smaller units and / or attachment of additional biochemical moieties including oligosaccharides, lipids or phosphoryl groups) and taking into account the unique physico-chemical properties of each proteoform, the number of potential protein species that need to be measured grows significantly: estimated for humans at 2,000,000²⁵.

Typically, the focus of proteomics methodologies is on identification and quantitation of peptides (i.e. smaller fragments that are generated by shearing naturally occurring proteins found in a sample) that are then used to infer the relative abundance of open reading frame (ORF) products between samples. The general method can be summarised into four core elements (see also **Figure 1**):

- **Standardised and sample-specific processing protocols** to ensure reproducible comparisons across many samples or replicates. This can include the isolation or enrichment of specific sub-proteomes²⁶;
- **Fractionation** to reduce proteome complexity to a level that can be managed by the analysis instrument;
- **Mass spectrometry** (MS) with a suitable instrument that is configured for the required experiment to measure the mass-to-charge ratio of molecules in the sample, and;
- **Bioinformatics** that may include spectrum identification, protein inference, quality control and protein quantitation, as well as numerous optional post-analysis steps

Figure 1 highlights a hypothetical proteomics workflow with a focus on the bioinformatics approach taken. In the example, a straightforward protein quantitation experiment will reproducibly process two or more biological samples (e.g. fluid, tissue) in parallel to extract

¹⁹ Lill J.R. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14789450.2021.1962300>

²⁰ Human Proteome Organisation [Proteomics Timeline](https://www.hupo.org/Proteomics-Timeline) <https://www.hupo.org/Proteomics-Timeline>

²¹ Omenn G.S. *et al.* 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jproteome.0c00485>

²² <https://www.uniprot.org/>

²³ Canonical, or where the term “protein” refers to the product of an Open Reading Frame rather than a true proteoform.

²⁴ UniProt proteome search and filter: https://www.uniprot.org/proteomes/?query=*&fil=reference%3Ayes

²⁵ Ponomarenko, E.A. *et al.* 2016, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4889822/>

²⁶ For example, phosphorylation is a crucial signalling modification that requires enrichment prior to analysis due to its low abundance

proteins for purification, concentration, chemical derivatisation (e.g. tandem mass tags TMT²⁷ or isobaric tagging for relative and absolute quantitation iTRAQ²⁸) and proteolytic digestion (grey boxes): the resulting complex peptide mixtures are separated by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC; green box) and introduced directly into a MS instrument (orange box). Here, the mass-to-charge ratio and intensity are measured for detected peptides as well as the product ions²⁹ created following induced fragmentation of selected peptides (orange boxes). A subsequent (hypothetical) bioinformatics workflow could include data conversion prior to peptide identification, protein inference and quality control, as well as quantitation and other post-analyses (blue boxes)³⁰. Protein PTMs (e.g. glycosylation and phosphorylation), structural features (e.g. mutations, domains) and protein-protein interactions (e.g. composition and stoichiometry of complexes) may be annotated^{31, 32}. Additional post-analysis steps may also be implemented to provide biological context for a list of quantified proteins, including statistics³³, classification³⁴, gene ontology³⁵ enrichment analysis (i.e. inferring molecular function, cellular component, biological process) or pathway mapping (e.g. using KEGG³⁶).

²⁷ Thompson A., Schäfer J., *et al.*, 2003 <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac0262560>

²⁸ Ross P. L., Huang Y. N., *et al.* 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1074/mcp.m400129-mcp200>

²⁹ http://mass-spec.lsu.edu/msterms/index.php/Product_ion

³⁰ Noor Z., Ahn S. B., *et al.* 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbz163>

³¹ Doll S., Gnad F. & Mann M. 2019, <https://dx.doi.org/10.1002%2Fprca.201800113>

³² Aebersold R. & Mann M. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature19949>

³³ Huang T. *et al.* 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1074/mcp.RA120.002105>

³⁴ Föll M.C. *et al.* 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12014-022-09347-z>

³⁵ Gene Ontology overview <http://geneontology.org/docs/ontology-documentation/>

³⁶ KEGG <https://www.genome.jp/kegg/>

Figure 1: A general (hypothetical) proteomics bioinformatics workflow

The wet-lab experimental parts of the workflow includes sample processing (grey), fractionation (green), mass spectrometry (MS, orange) and bioinformatics (blue). The peptide and protein identification process is heavily reliant on comparison of MS data to pre-existing databases (e.g. UniProt proteomes), or spectral libraries in some workflows. Once identification and protein inference has been completed, data has to be managed, proteins may be quantified, and other post-analyses may be completed, including inferring protein functions using the Gene Ontology, pathway mapping as well as structural or post-translational modification analysis. In isolation or combination, these analyses allow the researcher to draw biological meaning or understanding, in the context of the original experimental question that prompted sample collection. This workflow was adapted from information detailed in Noor *et al.* 2021³⁷.

Several important key features of proteomics worth noting include:

- **A reliance on specialised instrument platforms:** almost invariably, proteomics relies on expensive and sophisticated specialist instruments for chromatography and mass spectrometry that require significant expertise and time commitment to operate effectively. Most instruments make use of matrix assisted laser / desorption ionisation (MALDI) or electrospray ionisation (ESI) to ionise samples. In contrast, the number of mass analysers available is far greater, and includes time-of-flight (ToF), ion trap, quadrupole ion trap, triple quadrupoles (QqQ), Fourier transform ion cyclotron resonance (FTICR) and Orbitrap systems.
- **A requirement for explicit descriptions of experimental context:** to quote an Australian community member who has been involved in our community consultations “a *spectrum is not just a spectrum*”. To be understood and used to answer biological

³⁷ Noor Z. *et al.* 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbz163>

questions, it is critical that the context behind the creation of mass spectra is clear, including sample, preparation / processing steps and instrument settings.

- **The MS instruments continually and rapidly evolve:** new instruments are regularly released by vendors, and this includes next generation systems (e.g. ion mobility separation). With each new system released, methods for optimal application and downstream bioinformatics need to adapt.
- **Specialised requirements depending on biological question and sample type:**
 - **Specialised** approaches are often necessary when analysing different biological systems: e.g. for single cell proteomics (low sample amounts)³⁸, membrane and PTM proteomics (specific chemistries)³⁹ and serum proteomics (bio-fluid composition and concentration ranges)⁴⁰.
 - **Targeted and untargeted** approaches are often used to either assay for changes in specific targets, or ascertain the broader biological impact of a condition or intervention⁴¹, respectively.
 - **Top-down** (intact protein) and **bottom-up** (proteolytic peptide product) approaches may be used depending on the biological question and the sample preparation required⁴².

Other important, aspects to consider when comparing proteomics with other omics-based approaches such as genomics include:

- **There is no method to amplify protein material**⁴³: there is no equivalent in proteomics to the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) that is used to amplify nucleic acids (DNA / RNA). Dynamic range of protein concentration of some samples (e.g. plasma) is also greater (10+ orders of magnitude) than instrument dynamic range (~5 orders of magnitude). Sample availability and preparation is therefore a prime consideration.
- **Many proteomics researchers are reliant on vendor-supplied software solutions** that are tightly wedded to the instrument, and the open source movement in proteomics is therefore not as mature as in genomics.

3.2 International proteomics efforts

The international proteomics community is supported by a network of well established and professionally run bioinformatics and proteomics data-centric infrastructures, including neXtProt

³⁸ Kelly R.T. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1074/mcp.R120.002234>

³⁹ Chernykh A. *et al.* 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1042/BST20200222>

⁴⁰ Geyer P. *et al.* 2017, <https://doi.org/10.15252/msb.20156297>

⁴¹ Manes N.P. and Nita-Lazar A. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jprot.2018.02.008>

⁴² Kar U.K., Simonian M. & Whitelegge J.P. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14789450.2017.1359545>

⁴³ Cox J. and Mann M. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2007.07.032>

⁴⁴, the Human Protein Atlas⁴⁵ and ProteomeXchange⁴⁶, which includes Proteomics Identification Database (PRIDE)⁴⁷ and PeptideAtlas⁴⁸.

Human proteomics is represented internationally by the Human Proteome Project (HPP)⁴⁹, which has confidently identified more than 90% of the proteome⁵⁰, and is underpinned by integration of chromosome, disease and technology-centric annotations⁵¹.

Non-human proteomics currently represents 58.6% of all submitted research data in ProteomeXchange, and effective leveraging of proteogenomics is expected to increase this, as efforts to preserve and benefit from biodiversity are accelerated by study of non-model organisms at scale^{52,53}.

In Europe, the intergovernmental organisation ELIXIR⁵⁴ supports and collaborates with multiple communities, including Proteomics. The ELIXIR Proteomics community was first described in 2017 and identified the following priority areas: 1) multiomics, 2) proteoforms and PTMs, 3) quality control, 4) data analysis workflows and cloud computing, 5) protein quantification and statistics as well as 6) metadata, standardisation, annotation and data management⁵⁵. The community has run multiple implementation studies⁵⁶, and is an important international exemplar for the integration of a community with research platforms (data, tools, interoperability, compute and training)⁵⁷.

Australian research leaders are prominent internationally, and have contributed to the executive and science advisory for the HPP⁵⁸, the proteome for Human Chromosome 7⁵⁹ and the GlyGen glycosylation database⁶⁰.

⁴⁴ neXtProt <https://www.nextprot.org/>

⁴⁵ Human Protein Atlas <https://www.proteinatlas.org/>

⁴⁶ ProteomeXchange <http://www.proteomexchange.org/>

⁴⁷ Proteomics Identification Database (PRIDE) <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pride/>

⁴⁸ PeptideAtlas <http://www.peptideatlas.org/>

⁴⁹ Human Proteome Project (HPP): <https://hupo.org/human-proteome-project>

⁵⁰ Omenn G.S. et al., 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jproteome.0c00485>

⁵¹ About the Human Proteome Project: <https://hupo.org/About-the-HPP>

⁵² Yates JR III. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jproteome.0c00607>

⁵³ Heck M. & Neely BA. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jproteome.0c00448>

⁵⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us>

⁵⁵ Vizcaino J.A., Walzer M. et al. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.11751.1>

⁵⁶ Extending open proteomics data analysis pipelines in the cloud [2018-2019]

<https://elixir-europe.org/internal-projects/commissioned-services/extending-proteomics-pipelines>

Crowd-sourcing the annotation of public proteomics datasets to improve data reusability [2018-2020]

<https://elixir-europe.org/internal-projects/commissioned-services/crowd-sourcing-proteomics>

Comparison, benchmarking and dissemination of proteomics data analysis pipelines [2019-2021]

<https://elixir-europe.org/internal-projects/commissioned-services/proteomics-pipelines>

Increasing the translational value of public proteomics datasets [2021-2023]

<https://elixir-europe.org/internal-projects/commissioned-services/increasing-value-proteomics-datasets>

⁵⁷ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms>

⁵⁸ HuPO leadership: <https://hupo.org/HPP-leadership>

⁵⁹ HuPO chromosome team 7: <https://hupo.org/chr.7> & <https://projects.ands.org.au/id/AP32>

⁶⁰ GlyGen glycosylation database <https://www.glygen.org/> & York WS. et al. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1093/glycob/cwz080>

3.3 Who in Australia is performing proteomics and what is their focus?

Proteomics is critical to research in Australia, and is noted within multiple Australian Academy of Science Decadal Plans for Science, including Agriculture (2017)⁶¹, Marine Biodiversity (2018)⁶² and Nutrition (2019)⁶³: i.e. proteomics is described as one of several important disciplines that should be applied in combination to understand genome to phenome connections, to drive the creation of innovative approaches, and to study the nutritional impact on health and disease endpoints, respectively.

There are multiple societies that represent Australian proteomics researchers:

- The Australasian Proteomics Society (APS)⁶⁴, which represents proteomics nationally and hosts the annual Lorne Proteomics Symposium⁶⁵;
- The Australia and New Zealand Society for Mass Spectrometry⁶⁶ (ANZSMS), who represent the mass spectrometry research community (including proteomics) nationally, and;
- Proteomics & Metabolomics Victoria (PMV)⁶⁷.

There are also multiple facilities, consortia, institutes and funded projects that drive the application of proteomics in Australian research, including:

⁶¹ [Australian Academy of Science Agriculture Decadal Plan \(2017\)](https://www.science.org.au/files/userfiles/support/reports-and-plans/2017/agricultural-decadal-plan-2017-26.pdf)

<https://www.science.org.au/files/userfiles/support/reports-and-plans/2017/agricultural-decadal-plan-2017-26.pdf>

⁶² [Australian Academy of Science Marine Science Decadal Plan \(2018\)](https://www.marinescience.net.au/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/National-Marine-Science-Plan.pdf)

<https://www.marinescience.net.au/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/National-Marine-Science-Plan.pdf>

⁶³ [Australian Academy of Science Nutrition Decadal Plan \(2019\)](https://www.science.org.au/files/userfiles/support/reports-and-plans/2019/2019-nutrition-decadal-plan.pdf)

<https://www.science.org.au/files/userfiles/support/reports-and-plans/2019/2019-nutrition-decadal-plan.pdf>

⁶⁴ Australasian Proteomics Society (APS) <https://www.australasianproteomics.org/>

⁶⁵ Lorne Proteomics Symposium <https://www.lorneproteomics.org/>

⁶⁶ Australian and New Zealand Society for Mass Spectrometry (ANZSMS) <https://www.anzsms.org/>

⁶⁷ Proteomics & Metabolomics Victoria <http://pmv.org.au/>

- The Australasian Core Facilities⁶⁸ group, currently composed of more than 30 mass spectrometry facilities across Australia and New Zealand. These facilities centralise infrastructure and expertise in experimental proteomics and downstream bioinformatics, making it realistic for researchers to address the plethora of analytical approaches in proteomics. Each facility typically also specialises in specific analysis approaches that are determined by sample type, disease state or domains (e.g. agriculture or clinical proteomics), as well as by research interest, expertise and infrastructure availability. Life

⁶⁸ Joint Mass Spectrometry Facility (Australian National University)

<https://chemistry.anu.edu.au/research/facilities/joint-mass-spectrometry-facility>,

Australian Proteome Analysis Facility (Macquarie University)

<https://www.mq.edu.au/research/research-centres-groups-and-facilities/facilities/australian-proteome-analysis-facility>, Bioanalytical Mass Spectrometry Facility (University of New South Wales) <https://www.analytical.unsw.edu.au/facilities/bmsf>, Sydney Mass Spectrometry (University of Sydney) <https://www.sydney.edu.au/research/facilities/sydney-mass-spectrometry.html>, Mass Spectrometry Facility (University of Sydney)

<https://www.sydney.edu.au/science/our-research/research-facilities/chemistry-facilities.html>, Proteomics Core Facility (University of Technology Sydney) <https://www.uts.edu.au/about/faculty-science/biosciences-and-proteomics-technologies/about-us>, Mass Spectrometry Facility (Western Sydney University)

https://www.westernsydney.edu.au/research/centralised_research_facilities/mass_spectrometry, Biomedical Proteomics (Children's Medical Research Institute) <https://www.cmrijeansforgenes.org.au/research/research-facilities/biomedical-proteomics>, Biological Mass Spectrometry (University of Newcastle)

<https://www.newcastle.edu.au/research/facilities/central-analytical-facilities/abrf/biological-mass-spectrometry>, Mass Spectrometry User Resource & Research Facility (University of Wollongong)

<https://www.uow.edu.au/science-medicine-health/research/biomasspec/>, The Freedman Foundation Metabolomics Facility (Victor Chang Cardiac Research Institute) <https://www.victorchang.edu.au/innovation-centre/metabolomics>, Mass Spectrometry Facility

(Institute for Molecular Bioscience, University of Queensland) <https://imb.uq.edu.au/mass-spectrometry>, Proteomics Facility (Translational Research Institute, University of Queensland) <https://www.tri.edu.au/proteomics>, Mass Spectrometry Facility (Centre for Clinical Research, University of Queensland) <https://clinical-research.centre.uq.edu.au/services/mass-spectrometry-services>, Central Analytical Research Facility (Queensland University of Technology)

<https://www.qut.edu.au/research/why-qut/infrastructure/central-analytical-research-facility>, Queensland Bioscience Precinct, St Lucia (Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation), Advanced Mass Spectrometry Laboratory (Griffith University)

<https://www.griffith.edu.au/institute-glycomics/about-us/our-facilities/advanced-mass-spectrometry-facility>, Flinders Omics Facility (Flinders University) <https://www.flinders.edu.au/health-medical-research-institute/facilities/omics>, Adelaide Proteomics Centre

(University of Adelaide) <https://set.adelaide.edu.au/our-research/facilities-services/adelaide-proteomics-centre>, Mass Spectrometry and Proteomics (MSP) Facility (University of South Australia)

<https://www.unisa.edu.au/research/mass-spectrometry-and-proteomics/>, Metabolomics SA (University of Adelaide)

<https://metabolomics.awri.com.au/>, SAHMRI Mass Spectrometry (South Australian Health and Medical Research Institute)

<https://research.sahmri.org.au/en/organisations/mass-spectrometry>, UTas Proteomics Mass Spectrometry (University of Tasmania)

<https://www.utas.edu.au/central-science-laboratory/facilities/proteomics-mass-spectrometry>, Metabolomics Australia (University of Melbourne) <https://www.bio21.unimelb.edu.au/metabolomics-australia>, Monash Proteomic & Metabolomic Facility (Monash University)

<https://www.monash.edu/researchinfrastructure/mpmf>, Bio21 Mass Spectrometry and Proteomics (University of Melbourne)

<https://www.bio21.unimelb.edu.au/mass-spectrometry-and-proteomics>, WEHI Proteomics (Walter and Eliza Hall Institute of Medical Research) <https://www.wehi.edu.au/research/research-technologies/proteomics>, MassDynamics

<https://www.massdynamics.com/>, Proteomics and Metabolomics Platform (LaTrobe University)

<https://www.latrobe.edu.au/research-infrastructure/research-facilities/proteomics-and-metabolomics-platform>, Baker Molecular

Proteomics (Baker Heart and Diabetes Institute) <https://www.baker.edu.au/research/laboratories/molecular-proteomics>, Proteomics International Laboratories <https://www.proteomics.com.au/>, Western Australian Proteomics Facility (University of Western Australia)

<https://www.cmca.uwa.edu.au/facilities/wa-proteomics-facility>, Science Analytical Facility (Edith Cowan University)

<https://www.ecu.edu.au/schools/science/research/analytical-facility>, Mass Spectrometry Hub (MaSH, University of Auckland)

<https://mash.auckland.ac.nz/>, Centre for Protein Research (Otago University) <https://www.otago.ac.nz/protein/index.html>, Mass

Spectrometry Facility (Victoria University) <https://www.uvic.ca/science/chemistry/research/technicalservices/mass-spec/index.php>,

School of Natural Sciences (Massey University), Mass Spectrometry Facility (University of Canterbury)

<https://www.canterbury.ac.nz/science/schools/phys-chem/facilities/>, AgResearch Proteomics

<https://www.agresearch.co.nz/proteomics>

science researchers converge on these facilities to undertake proteomics for their biological questions;

- The Australian Research Council (ARC) Centre of Excellence (CoE) for Innovations in Peptide and Protein Science (CIPPS)⁶⁹;
- The recently completed multi-omics Framework Initiative for clinically relevant microorganisms, the Antibiotic Resistant Sepsis Pathogens Initiative⁷⁰;
- The Plant Protein Atlas Framework Initiative for pulse crop multiomics⁷¹;
- The Australian Cancer Research Foundation (ACRF) International Centre for the Proteome of Human Cancer (ProCan)⁷²;
- From 2020 to 2022, multiple grants were awarded to projects that featured “proteome” or “proteomics”:
 - 19 National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC) projects⁷³
 - 11 ARC Discovery and DECRA projects⁷⁴

In practice, Australian proteomics impacts clinical, environmental and agricultural research, in addition to the basic research which tackles novel methods and fundamental mechanisms of mass spectrometry. **Figure 2** highlights the growing number of proteomics and mass spectrometry peer reviewed publications co-authored by Australian researchers (**2a**), as compared to all proteomics publications (**2b**) over the past several decades.

⁶⁹ Australian Research Council (ARC) Centre of Excellence (CoE) for Innovations in Peptide and Protein Science (CIPPS) <https://cipps.org.au/>

⁷⁰ Antibiotic Resistant Sepsis Pathogens Framework Initiative (Bioplatforms Australia) <https://bioplatforms.com/projects/sepsis/>

⁷¹ Plant Protein Atlas Framework Initiative (Bioplatforms Australia) <https://bioplatforms.com/projects/plant-protein-atlas-initiative/>

⁷² ProCan <https://www.cmrijeansforgenes.org.au/research/research-teams/procan/about-procan>

⁷³ NHMRC funding outcomes - searching for “proteomics” or “proteome” as key words <https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/funding/data-research/outcomes>

⁷⁴ Australian Research Council Discovery Projects - searching for “proteomics” or “proteome” <https://www.arc.gov.au/news-publications/media/funding-announcement-kits/discovery-projects-2022>

Figure 2a: Estimates of the increasing number of proteomics and mass spectrometry studies conducted in Australia

To gain an estimate of the number of proteomics studies that have been conducted historically in Australia, a search was conducted of the Scopus database⁷⁵ for articles with: either (A) 'proteomics' (B) 'proteome' or (C) 'mass AND spectrometry' in the title, abstract, or keyword and 'australia' in the affiliation. The complete list of citations including authors, titles and journals can be [found here](#).

⁷⁵ Scopus database <https://www.elsevier.com/solutions/scopus>

Figure 2b: Comparison of proteomics studies conducted in Australia and globally

To gain an estimate of the number of proteomics studies that have been conducted historically in Australia and globally, a search was conducted of the Scopus database for articles with 'proteomics' in the title, abstract, or keyword and both with and without 'australia' in the affiliation.

To appreciate the breadth of projects being undertaken and published, a text mining approach was used to reveal the top ten title words in publications which were co-authored by Australian researchers from 2016 onwards: these were *human*, *cancer*, *cell(s)*, *disease*, *extracellular*, *identification*, *molecular*, *response* and *biomarkers*. This highlights a focus on identifying responses to a specific condition, particularly in cellular pathologies like cancer, but also the importance of biomarker discovery as a science driver for proteomics. However, there is also great diversity in the long tail of proteomics publications. To highlight this, for example, sampling the first six publications of 2022 co-authored by Australian researchers reveals work that is focused across a diverse range of topics, including identification of antimicrobials against *Salmonella*⁷⁶, mitochondrial protein analysis methods⁷⁷, antigen identification for vaccine development⁷⁸, cross species blood plasma proteomics⁷⁹, a comparison of milk fat and whey proteomes in camels⁸⁰ and protein extraction methods for narrow-leafed lupin seeds⁸¹.

⁷⁶ Majak Gut A. *et al.* 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.idairyj.2021.105180>

⁷⁷ Tang A. *et al.* 2022, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-0716-1653-6_11

⁷⁸ Luu L.D.W. & Lan R. 2022, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-0716-1900-1_4

⁷⁹ Noor Z. *et al.* 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jprot.2021.104384>

⁸⁰ Han B. *et al.* 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2021.130658>

⁸¹ Tahmasian A. *et al.* 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2021.130722>

3.4 Engaging the proteomics community in Australia

In August 2020 the Australian BioCommons invited researchers from across Australia who undertake either MS based proteomics or metabolomics analysis to participate in a MS SIG. The BioCommons sought information from the SIG members via an online survey⁸² and a follow up video conference (in September 2020) (the agenda, minutes and recording are available⁸³). The survey was left open and advertised for 8 months (i.e. into Q1 2021) to collect as many responses as possible (final number of respondents = 32). In November 2021 we subsequently also consulted with the Australasian Core Facilities (ACF) group at their annual meeting, hosting a session that was focussed on documenting bioinformatics IT infrastructure challenges encountered by members of the ACF when undertaking either proteomics or metabolomics analyses (summary available⁸⁴). Finally, in 2022 the BioCommons established a working group together with the ACF and a quarterly Proteomics Community Consultation⁸⁵, to continue refining requirements.

From this point on in this document, the proteomics specific information gleaned throughout these consultations are described: the aim is to give a holistic view of Australian proteomics and the bioinformatics challenges facing this group of researchers.

The online survey revealed that the majority of the 32 respondents undertake proteomics (N = 27) and 15 of those solely focus on proteomics or meta-proteomics. Of the 27 who work in proteomics, 12 also work in metabolomics. This indicates a skew towards proteomics, but also that many community members work across both areas.

A snapshot of the survey respondents who undertake proteomics analysis is as follows:

Within the group of 27 survey respondents who undertake proteomics, the predominant application areas for proteomic analysis were in *human health / medical* (N = 17), *fundamental bio-research* (N = 14) and *agriculture* (N = 13). Both *food & beverage* (N = 9) and *environmental research* (N = 7) were also well represented. The most studied sample types were *microorganisms (e.g. cultures, isolates)* (N = 20), *tissues (e.g. heart, liver, brain)* (N = 20), *fluids (e.g. blood, serum, urine)* (N = 19), *environmental samples* (N = 9) and *plants* (N = 4).

The responses also revealed that a wide range of processes that are required to undertake a proteomic experiment will be performed over the next 5 years by this group. These include liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry, labelled quantitation (SILAC⁸⁶, iTRAQ⁸⁷, TMT⁸⁸), label-free quantitation (LFQ), mass spectrometry only (e.g. direct surface analysis, infusion), data pre-processing and management, mass spectrometry assay development, shot-gun peptide

⁸² See [Appendix 3](#) for the Survey questions, a presentation including survey results for mass spectrometry infrastructure needs and challenges (last response in March 2021) is available here:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1tDhS7RfM2ZfRPooWqjAXXVu24pALoCaJ>

⁸³ Agenda and minutes with links to the presentation (including survey results for infrastructure needs and challenges):

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/18ANmg8gEIWf4sxiXostOnX5qneQj--Q15GdULJYxkpl/edit>

⁸⁴ Summary of the 2021 Australasian Core Facilities (ACF) meeting:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/10C4ZMewuBfgMeEZVuWLOUR0L_RihKFSOBQeipujY7zQ/edit#heading=h.ipf0msv8i33ji

⁸⁵ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/proteomics-bioinformatics>

⁸⁶ Stable-isotope labelling by amino acids in cell culture (SILAC): Mann M. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrm2067>

⁸⁷ Isobaric tag for relative and absolute quantitation (iTRAQ): Wiese S. *et al.* 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pmic.200600422>

⁸⁸ Tandem mass tags (TMTs): Thompson A. *et al.* 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac0262560>

identification, statistical analyses, bioinformatics tool implementation and bioinformatics tool development.

Detailed results from the survey are presented in section 3.5 below and this has been supplemented where appropriate with additional relevant information gleaned via additional meetings (e.g. BioCommons session at the 2021 ACF meeting, ACF working group).

3.5 How is proteomics being undertaken in Australia?

Proteomics is a method for characterising proteomes and multiple different aspects of these proteomes, including sequence, quantity, modifications and structure. As a result the approaches, data and tools used are diverse.

3.5.1 Data

The survey responses indicated that the majority of proteomics users in this group employ Orbitrap⁸⁹ (N = 26), ToF/ToF⁹⁰ (N = 12), QqQ⁹¹ (N = 11) and Q-ToF⁹² (N = 7) mass spectrometry instruments to generate data.

Of the SIG proteomics users, 100% of respondents (N = 27) make use of public data from UniProt⁹³ (the premier international database that stores protein sequence and function information), and 9 other databases: AllFam⁹⁴, EnsemblPlants⁹⁵, KEGG⁹⁶, mzCloud⁹⁷, NCBI⁹⁸, PeptideAtlas⁹⁹, PRIDE¹⁰⁰, SRM Atlas¹⁰¹ and SwissProt (the expertly curated component of UniProt). Custom databases were used by 52% of the proteomics respondents (N = 14).

A wide variety of data management solutions are used by the community, including custom solutions, in-house built tools or use of Microsoft Excel files, as well as data management systems or platforms: Microsoft Sharepoint¹⁰², iLab¹⁰³, MyTardis¹⁰⁴, SCIEX Cloud¹⁰⁵, LabArchives¹⁰⁶, OpenBIS¹⁰⁷ and the Bioplatforms Australia Data Portal¹⁰⁸.

⁸⁹ ThermoFisher Orbitrap systems

<https://www.thermofisher.com/au/en/home/industrial/mass-spectrometry/liquid-chromatography-mass-spectrometry-lc-ms/lc-ms-systems/orbitrap-lc-ms.html>

⁹⁰ Suckau D. *et al.*, 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-003-2057-0>

⁹¹ Yost R.A. & Enke C.G., 1978, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja00475a072>

⁹² Li C. *et al.* 2021, <https://dx.doi.org/10.3389%2Ffchem.2021.813359>

⁹³ UniProt/SwissProt <https://www.uniprot.org/>

⁹⁴ AllFam: <http://www.meduniwien.ac.at/allfam/browse.php?>

⁹⁵ EnsemblPlants <https://plants.ensembl.org/index.html>

⁹⁶ KEGG <https://www.genome.jp/kegg/>

⁹⁷ mzCloud <https://www.mzcloud.org/>

⁹⁸ NCBI <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>

⁹⁹ PeptideAtlas <http://www.peptideatlas.org/>

¹⁰⁰ PRIDE <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pride/>

¹⁰¹ SRM Atlas <http://www.srmatlas.org/>

¹⁰² Microsoft Sharepoint <https://www.microsoft.com/en-au/microsoft-365/sharepoint/collaboration>

¹⁰³ Agilent iLab <https://www.agilent.com/en/products/lab-management-software/core-facility-management/ilab-business-intelligence>

¹⁰⁴ MyTardis <http://www.mytardis.org/>

¹⁰⁵ SCIEX Cloud <https://sciex.com/tech-notes/life-science-research/multi-omics/architecture-and-security-overview---sciex-cloud>

¹⁰⁶ LabArchives <https://www.labarchives.com/>

¹⁰⁷ OpenBIS <https://openbis.ch/>

¹⁰⁸ Bioplatforms Australia Data Portal <https://data.bioplatforms.com/>

Sharing data is also achieved using multiple different solutions, including:

- Data transfer via email or on physical devices including USBs, but also;
- Commercial data management and sharing solutions including MyTardis, Google Drive¹⁰⁹, Dropbox¹¹⁰, Panorama¹¹¹, OneDrive¹¹², Spotfire¹¹³, Microsoft SharePoint⁸⁶ and LabArchives⁹⁰;
- The Australian Academic Research Network (AARNet)¹¹⁴ service CloudStor¹¹⁵, including FileSender;
- The Nectar Cloud¹¹⁶;
- Institutional repositories such as CSIRO DAP (Data Access Portal)¹¹⁷ and UQ's Research Data Manager (RDM)¹¹⁸;
- The Bioplatforms Australia Data Portal, and;
- International repositories such as PRIDE.

Other, more bespoke solutions used by community members include *in-house* data management systems, network drives (including in-house or shared group drives), cloud applications and storage folders (including local) as well as online safe data transfer systems.

The majority of proteomics respondents make their data publicly available (N = 17) with three of these respondents indicating that the submission process presented challenges. Two respondents explicitly indicated that they do not make their data publicly available.

The main reason given for not sharing data is due to commercial confidence issues (N = 7 responses). One community member indicated they do not know how to make data publicly available, and one did not see a benefit to data sharing.

3.5.2 Tools

The survey responses indicated that the group made use of 19 open source and 22 proprietary software packages and workflows. These are detailed in [Appendix 1](#) and [Appendix 2](#) respectively, and cover many different analytical aspects. Each appendix has also been supplemented by software tools and workflows identified through on-going consultations with the community.

A greater reliance on proprietary software (as opposed to genomics-based analysis approaches noted for Genome Assembly¹¹⁹ and Genome Annotation¹²⁰ communities, for example) is a key

¹⁰⁹ Drive.google.com <https://drive.google.com>

¹¹⁰ Dropbox <https://www.dropbox.com/>

¹¹¹ Panorama <https://www.ebsco.com/products/panorama>

¹¹² OneDrive <https://onedrive.live.com/about/en-us/signin/>

¹¹³ Spotfire <https://www.tibco.com/products/tibco-spotfire>

¹¹⁴ Australian Academic Research Network <https://www.aarnet.edu.au/>

¹¹⁵ CloudStor <https://www.aarnet.edu.au/cloudstor>

¹¹⁶ Nectar Research Cloud <https://ardc.edu.au/services/nectar-research-cloud/>

¹¹⁷ CSIRO Data Access Portal <https://data.csiro.au/collections>

¹¹⁸ UQ RDM <https://research.uq.edu.au/rmbt/uqrdm>

¹¹⁹ Genome Assembly Infrastructure Roadmap for Australia <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3967969>

¹²⁰ Genome Annotation Infrastructure Roadmap for Australia <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3942715>

feature of mass spectrometry and proteomics, with such software often supplied alongside a specific instrument by the vendor.

The near equal split between open source and proprietary software tools noted in the SIG survey responses was also reiterated at the 2021 ACF Annual Meeting, with 39% of meeting attendees indicating that their facility predominantly employed proprietary software and a further 36% of attendees indicating that their facility utilise proprietary and open source software solutions in approximately equal measure¹²¹.

The tools being employed for proteomics data analysis by more than one survey respondent are as follows. Proprietary tools are indicated in **bold**, and free-to-use / open source tools in plain (non-bold) text:

- MaxQuant¹²² (N = 15);
- R / RStudio¹²³ (N = 15);
- **SCIEX software suite (which includes general SCIEX software¹²⁴, PeakView¹²⁵, ProteinPilot¹²⁶ and MultiQuant¹²⁷** (N = 14);
- Perseus¹²⁸ (N = 10);
- Python¹²⁹ / Jupyter Notebook (N = 11);
- **Proteome Discoverer¹³⁰** (N = 9);
- Percolator¹³¹ (N = 9);
- Morpheus¹³² (N = 9);
- Custom tool developed in our group or by collaborators (N = 7);
- **Spectronaut¹³³** (N = 6);
- **Mascot¹³⁴** (N = 4);
- Skyline¹³⁵ (N = 4);
- **Byonic¹³⁶** (N = 4);
- **Mass Dynamics¹³⁷** (N = 4);
- **PEAKS¹³⁸** (N = 3);

¹²¹ ACF meeting BioCommons Session Summary (2021)

https://docs.google.com/document/d/10C4ZMewuBfgMeEZVuWLOUR0L_RihKFSOBQeipuiY7zQ/edit#

¹²² MaxQuant <https://www.maxquant.org/> / <https://bio.tools/maxquant>

¹²³ The R Project for Statistical Computing (<https://www.r-project.org/>) and RStudio (<https://www.rstudio.com/>)

¹²⁴ SCIEX software <https://sciex.com/products/software>

¹²⁵ SCIEX PeakView <https://sciex.com/products/software/peakview-software>

¹²⁶ SCIEX ProteinPilot <https://sciex.com/products/software/proteinpilot-software>

¹²⁷ SCIEX MultiQuant <https://sciex.com/products/software/multiquant-software>

¹²⁸ Perseus <https://www.maxquant.org/perseus/> / <https://bio.tools/perseus>

¹²⁹ Python <https://www.python.org/>

¹³⁰ ThermoFisher Scientific Proteome Discoverer

<https://www.thermofisher.com/au/en/home/industrial/mass-spectrometry/liquid-chromatography-mass-spectrometry-lc-ms/lc-ms-software/multi-omics-data-analysis/proteome-discoverer-software.html>

¹³¹ Percolator <http://percolator.ms/> / <https://bio.tools/percolator>

¹³² Morpheus <https://cwenger.github.io/Morpheus/> / <https://bio.tools/morpheus>

¹³³ BIOGNOSYS Spectronaut <https://biognosys.com/software/spectronaut/>

¹³⁴ Matrix Science Mascot <https://www.matrixscience.com/>

¹³⁵ Skyline <https://skyline.ms/>

¹³⁶ Protein Metrics Byos <https://proteinmetrics.com/byos/>

¹³⁷ Mass Dynamics <https://www.massdynamics.com/>

¹³⁸ Bioinformatics Solutions Peaks Studio <https://www.bioinfor.com/peaks-studio/>

- **CompoundDiscoverer**¹³⁹ (N = 2), and;
- **Scaffold**¹⁴⁰ (N = 2).

A relatively large proportion of the proteomics survey respondents use R / RStudio (N = 15), Python (N = 11) or custom tools (N = 7), which are open source and free-to-use. This contrasts with the quantitative proteomics tool MaxQuant (N = 15) and its downstream post-processing package Perseus (N = 10), which are free-to-use but not open source.

3.5.3 Compute infrastructure

3.5.3.1 Types used

The community members surveyed make use of multiple different computational resources ranging from high performance computing (HPC) (N = 25), local desktop / PC (N = 21) and commercial cloud (N = 12) - which includes resources like Amazon Web Services (AWS)¹⁴¹, Microsoft Azure¹⁴², and Google Cloud¹⁴³. Nectar cloud¹⁴⁴ was used by three SIG members.

Most HPC use is within an institution (N = 10) or research group (N = 11). Only two survey respondents use a national or state-based HPC capacity (e.g. at the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI)¹⁴⁵, Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre¹⁴⁶ or QCIF/QRISCloud¹⁴⁷).

3.5.3.2 IT expertise and resourcing

Many respondents reported that IT expertise to build and maintain compute infrastructure (e.g. installing and updating software) was available either within their institution (N = 15) or through other members of their research group (N = 11), while a smaller group reported an absence of specific IT expertise required to set up their infrastructure (N = 7).

3.6 Challenges being faced by the Australian proteomics community

3.6.1 Computational resourcing and set up challenges

In regards to computational resource availability, ten community members (of 18 responses, 55%) stated that their compute resource allocations were wholly or mostly sufficient now. Seven (39%) stated an immediate or pending need for more compute resources, and five (28%) stated that current compute infrastructure is insufficient.

More than half of the respondents (N = 17) indicated that the infrastructure currently accessible to them would not be sufficient 2 and 5 years into the future. The reasons given are that the

¹³⁹ ThermoFisher CompoundDiscoverer

<https://www.thermofisher.com/au/en/home/industrial/mass-spectrometry/liquid-chromatography-mass-spectrometry-lc-ms/lc-ms-software/multi-omics-data-analysis/compound-discoverer-software.html>

¹⁴⁰ Proteome Software Scaffold <https://www.proteomesoftware.com/products/scaffold-5>

¹⁴¹ <https://aws.amazon.com/>

¹⁴² <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-au/>

¹⁴³ <https://cloud.google.com/>

¹⁴⁴ Nectar research cloud <https://ardc.edu.au/services/nectar-research-cloud/>

¹⁴⁵ National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) <https://nci.org.au/>

¹⁴⁶ Pawsey Supercomputing Centre <https://pawsey.org.au/>

¹⁴⁷ Queensland CyberInfrastructure Foundation <https://www.qcif.edu.au/> / QRISCloud <https://www.qriscloud.org.au/>

respondents expect to be doing more mass spectrometry, and are already facing infrastructure challenges that include limitations in compute power (RAM and processor speed), a lack of sufficient storage space and a lack of access to expert IT support.

Looking to the future, six respondents indicated that their compute infrastructure will be sufficient in 2 years time (e.g. 2022-2023), and three respondents indicated sufficiency in 5 years time. There were 15 community members who indicated a lack of sufficient compute at the 2 year mark, which grew to 19 at the 5 year mark (2025-2026).

There were noted challenges with:

- Storage space;
- Processor / computational speed;
- Memory (RAM), and;
- Support for high-end computers (e.g. 32 cores, 3 TB storage) at the institution or in the research group.

It was also observed by multiple community members that more compute capacity is needed, and that potential issues in this space include problems finding appropriate infrastructure support locally and effectively engaging with infrastructure specialists.

The ACF group consultation supported this view, with attendees of the *Shared (Computational) Platforms* breakout group suggesting that HPC and cloud are desirable targets to host proteomics analysis, but access to systems of this type can be hampered by a lack of IT and system administration experience, especially for those based at smaller institutions with limited research computing IT support¹⁴⁸.

3.6.2 Data related challenges

Data movement and/or sharing using cloud-based technologies (e.g. Google Drive, CloudStor, Nectar Cloud, see section 3.3.1) predominates within this community. Wide spread data sharing challenges were not evident based on the community survey, with only one respondent identifying data transfer across Australia as a challenge.

However, a handful of respondents did identify challenges related to data storage space, including for large secondary or derived proteomics files, such as those produced by ProteomeDiscoverer¹⁴⁹.

The survey responses did not identify major challenges with data submission to international repositories, however one respondent did state that some repositories are inflexible with respect to submission content for certain data types (i.e. differing requirements for complete and partial submissions to PRIDE¹⁵⁰). Another annoyance expressed by one respondent was that they are required to store copies of data both on institutional data storage as well as through submission

¹⁴⁸ Summary: 2021 Australasian Core Facilities meeting

https://docs.google.com/document/d/10C4ZMewuBfgMeEZVuWLOUR0L_RihKFSOBQeipuiY7zQ/edit#heading=h.ipf0msv8i33i

¹⁴⁹ ThermoFisher Scientific ProteomeDiscoverer

<https://www.thermofisher.com/au/en/home/industrial/mass-spectrometry/liquid-chromatography-mass-spectrometry-lc-ms/lc-ms-software/multi-omics-data-analysis/teome-discoverer-software.html>

¹⁵⁰ Complete and partial submissions to Proteomics Identifications (PRIDE) database

https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pride/markdownpage/submitdatapage#complete_and_partial_submissions

to international repositories and that this represents a duplication of effort due to differing requirements between the two systems. Comments from a further four respondents noted that uploads can be hard work, “*public sites can be corrupting*” and uploading to PRIDE specifically can be difficult, in particular for large datasets.

3.6.3 Tool related challenges

The survey asked the community about challenges related to the suitability of tools and workflows for specific taxa or projects, but also if there were technical challenges in implementation of these resources.

The tool suitability challenges identified were:

- A general imbalance between analysis packages, resources and databases that are optimised for human proteome analysis as opposed to other organisms. Human-centric proteomic resources are well advanced in comparison to plants, for example.
- That some tools which may have broad applicability, are currently limited to the study of model organisms¹⁵¹ only, e.g. the multi omics analysis tool paintomics¹⁵², which was specifically mentioned as it is limited to model organisms only.
- The high intellectual barrier to using software, including open source, and a lack of time to explore new approaches and / or upskill. For example:
 - MaxQuant and Perseus (both free-to-use but not open source) are widely used and the intellectual commitment required to use either leaves limited time to explore other options that might be more user friendly.
 - A general lack of time to explore new approaches, tools and workflows: for example imputation free analysis and tools such as Triqler¹⁵³ and proDA¹⁵⁴.
- Due to significant costs associated with vendor-supplied software, access restrictions can arise as a result of licensing conditions of vendor-supplied software, tool and workflow solutions that arise due to budgetary constraints. For example, research groups often need to collectively share access to licensed software for a handful of proprietary tools, and restrictions may allow only one or several users to utilise the software at a particular point in time. This can create a significant bottleneck in throughput, especially when single analyses can sometimes take weeks or months to complete. Examples of proprietary tools where licensing restrictions may affect use include those listed in section 3.5.2, but also Shiny server¹⁵⁵ and SIMCA¹⁵⁶.

The technical challenges faced by the community when using tools and workflows included:

- A lack of availability of suitable computational infrastructure, with issues related to either memory, capacity or efficiency. Examples here include:

¹⁵¹ I.e. species that are widely studied, usually because they are easy to maintain and breed in a laboratory setting and have particular experimental advantages

¹⁵² Paintomics visualisation software <http://www.paintomics.org/>

¹⁵³ The M. and Käll L. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jproteome.0c00902>

¹⁵⁴ Ahlmann-Eltze C. and Anders S. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1101/661496>

¹⁵⁵ RStudio Shiny Server <https://www.rstudio.com/products/shiny/shiny-server/>

¹⁵⁶ Sartorius SIMCA

<https://www.sartorius.com/en/products/process-analytical-technology/data-analytics-software/mvda-software/simca>

- The memory and compute intensity of Skyline¹⁵⁷ for data independent analysis (DIA) is greater than resources available to some respondents;
 - MaxQuant¹⁵⁸, which is widely used by respondents, requires a large number of cores to run efficiently, which were not routinely available to some respondents, and;
 - The compute (wall) time required for some tools like Proteome Discoverer XlinkX¹⁵⁹ (which is used for cross-linking database searches) can extend beyond the general wall-time limits allowed on some computational systems.
- A lack of software solutions or outputs that are understandable by non-experts. One example is the High-Field Asymmetric Waveform Ion Mobility Spectrometry (FAIMS) method¹⁶⁰, where collaborators were not able to understand the software being used, and no suitable alternative software was available to provide clear and meaningful outputs.

3.6.4 The underlying training challenge

The need for a tailored and comprehensive proteomics training program was conveyed by the cumulative results of the survey and on-going consultations with the ACF. Groups such as ELIXIR proteomics have also previously identified the need for broad training programs that can support priority areas identified by the community¹⁶¹. Examples of the challenges described by the Australian proteomics community ranged from the inability to find support for using computational infrastructure (including gaining access to both HPC and cloud), complicated data uploads to international repositories, the intellectual barrier to reuse of open source software, a lack of time to upskill and a shortage of bioinformatics solutions suitable for end-users (i.e. non-bioinformaticians). It was also observed that the capabilities of proteomics, and the requirements of proteomics analyses, need to be clearer to end-user researchers. Collectively addressing this training challenge will need to be in the context of any new or adopted infrastructure solutions suggested for the Australian proteomics community in this roadmap.

3.7 Is a shared national solution desired by the research community?

A shared national solution has been delivered in Australia previously through the Australian Proteomics Computational Facility (APCF), which was funded by the National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC) from 2006-2012¹⁶². The APCF was a single advanced computing cluster that included a licensed copy of Mascot¹⁶³ software and several proteomics databases to enable protein identification¹⁶⁴. The cluster had more than 600 users representing

¹⁵⁷ Skyline <https://skyline.ms/project/home/software/Skyline/begin.view>

¹⁵⁸ MaxQuant: <https://www.maxquant.org/> / <https://bio.tools/maxquant>

¹⁵⁹ ProteomeDiscoverer XlinkX <https://www.hecklab.com/software/xlinkx/>

¹⁶⁰ High-Field Asymmetric Waveform Ion Mobility Spectrometry (FAIMS) <https://yost.chem.ufl.edu/research/faims/>

¹⁶¹ Vizcaino J.A., Walzer M. *et al.* 2017, <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.11751.1>

¹⁶² Australian Proteomics Computational Facility <http://purl.org/au-research/grants/nhmrc/381413>

¹⁶³ <https://www.matrixscience.com/>

¹⁶⁴ <https://www.wehi.edu.au/people/andrew-webb/1295/andrew-webb-resources>

more than 100 laboratory groups and was credited with supporting almost 200,000 searches to identify proteins¹⁶⁵. One SIG member specifically suggested bringing back the APCF, and went on to state that the APCF was “*the benchmark for a shared bioinformatics platform*”. There would be high value in examining which elements of the APCF were fit-for-purpose and could be translated to a new or re-imagined shared national solution.

Reinforcing this were more than 85% of the group (N = 21 of 27 total) indicating that they would use a shared compute infrastructure platform. This number included respondents who stated that their needs are currently met, but who would use a suitable shared platform (N = 19, 70%), and those who can't currently perform mass spectrometry without such a platform (N = 4). Potential challenges raised include the ease of use of such a platform, the potential difficulty of moving large experiments to a shared resource (e.g. TIMS-ToF experiment with 30 files is ~100GB), and a dependency on data security.

When survey respondents were asked about 22 general theoretical features (see survey section: *Characteristics of a shared analysis platform* in Appendix 3) of a shared platform that could support mass spectrometry related bioinformatics, the top 10 features (as determined by percentage of ‘crucial’ responses and listed here in descending order) are: (1) good documentation on how to use tools / pipelines & good documentation on how to use the platform, (3) easy to access from anywhere, (4) security of data and analysis, (5) easy to upload / download data, (6) following best practice in tools, formats and metadata, (7) ability to transfer data easily to / from storage, (8) assistance available in implementing pipelines & long-term support for and sustainability of the platform and (10) access to our preferred tools / pipelines & access to a choice of tools / pipelines. This is illustrated in **Figure 3**, which includes the responses for all proposed features.

¹⁶⁵ 2009-2018 NHMRC funding results
<https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/attachments/All-grants-2009-2018v3.xlsx>

Figure 3: Distilled SIG survey results for a shared proteomics platform

Survey results showing the criterion of a shared proteomics platform for bioinformatics, sorted by the percentage of respondents that indicated a criterion was crucial (yellow). Additional responses indicated that a criterion was considered either important (grey) or unimportant (blue).

4. Meeting the needs of Australian researchers for high-quality, accessible proteomics infrastructure

4.1 Goal / Aim

The Australian BioCommons aims to develop a 'Proteomics Infrastructure Roadmap for Australia' that describes collaborative infrastructure, which, when implemented (from Q3 2022 onwards), will enable Australian researchers from a wide range of institutions to perform high-quality proteomics who would otherwise be unable to do so because of data-, software- or compute-related infrastructure roadblocks.

Four versions of the roadmap are planned, each to incorporate content and feedback from different groups:

- Version 1 - content-based on SIG survey results and input from SIG meeting and bioinformatics session with the ACF group - April 2022.
- Version 2 - content modified to incorporate feedback from SIG - October 2022.

- Version 3 - content modified to incorporate feedback from international proteomics experts - November 2022.
- Version 4 - content modified to incorporate feedback from national computational infrastructure providers - December 2022

4.2 Objectives

The high level objectives of deploying the proposed infrastructure are:

- 1) To provide all Australian researchers with access to a shared platform with:
 - a) A selection of tools and workflows relevant for proteomics analysis of raw data;
 - b) The capacity to incorporate, complement and / or build upon the outputs of both open source and proprietary software hosted elsewhere;
 - c) Sufficient computational infrastructure and resources;
 - d) Connections to a variety of data storage locations and key datasets from public repositories, and;
 - e) Appropriate security and straightforward access mechanisms.
- 2) To make it easier for Australian researchers to perform secondary analyses, visualisation and exploratory data analysis for raw (primary) and derived (secondary) proteomics data;
- 3) To make it easier for researchers to publish high-quality reproducible proteomics data in accordance with best-practice open science guidelines, while accommodating the numerous different analysis types within proteomics;
- 4) To describe and coordinate a training program that will support the proteomics community to use data, software tools and workflows; and,
- 5) To address objectives one to four in the context of international proteomics efforts, aligning, adopting, collaborating and contributing where possible.

4.3 Outputs / Deliverables

To address the objectives, five broad outputs / infrastructure components are proposed for implementation.

D1. A shared platform for primary proteomics bioinformatics analyses;

D2. Interactive environments to enable secondary analyses, visualisation, and exploration of proteomics data, both raw and derived, and;

D3. Systems to enable submission and retrieval of raw (primary) and derived (secondary) proteomics data sets to / from appropriate global repositories

D4. A proteomics-specific bioinformatics training program, developed in conjunction with the proteomics community

D5. Alignment, adoption and contribution to global best-practice efforts

Figure 4. Diagram showing the proposed infrastructure to support Australian Proteomics

(D1) Shared platform for proteomics analyses. Mass spectrometry data, or other relevant data (e.g. databases, experimental configuration files), are inputs into the envisaged hypothetical shared platform for proteomics analyses, which provides both command-line interface (CLI)- or graphical user interface (GUI)-based access to proteomics relevant tools and workflows (blue shapes). This system is underpinned by sufficient and appropriate computational infrastructure. Closely associated with the shared platform is a data management platform (darker green shape) that caters to data management, version control, and association of appropriate (e.g. sample, experimental) metadata with the data files. Outputs of D1 are accessible to **(D2), an Interactive environment for statistical analyses and visualisation**, where common packages for secondary analysis, visualisation and exploration can be applied. The **(D3) Data publishing component** provides systems to enable submission and / or publishing of proteomics data (raw or derived) to international repositories. **(D4) Tailored training program** connects the proposed infrastructure to the BioCommons training program, and **(D5) Alignment to international best practice** highlights the aim to align, adopt and collaborate with international peer infrastructures to deliver the proposed infrastructure.

Arrows indicate the general flow of data. See Appendix 1 for a list of open source tools/pipelines that may be included in D1. Globe image: Clker-Free-Vector-Images, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons.

NOTE: The **Local, vendor supplied solutions** box indicated below D1 represents various proprietary proteomics analysis systems that are routinely operated independently by multiple research groups / MS facilities and which sit outside the envisaged system.

D1. A shared platform for primary proteomics bioinformatics analyses

To address objective 1 (i.e. providing Australian researchers with access to a selection of tools and workflows underpinned by sufficient and appropriate computational resources for proteomics analysis) it is proposed to implement a platform in Australia¹⁶⁶, that:

- A. Includes key software tools¹⁶⁷ and workflows¹⁶⁸ for analyses that include, but are not limited to, data conversion, processing, quality control, peptide/protein identification, quantitation and post-processing (pathway analysis, multi-omics):
 - a. Installed (dependencies included) on suitable command line interface (CLI) analysis environments (tier 1 and 2¹⁶⁹ HPC, but also both national and commercial cloud) where relevant, and underpinned by appropriate computational resources¹⁷⁰;
 - b. Installed and optimised on graphical user interface (GUI) cloud based analysis platforms (e.g. Galaxy Australia¹⁷¹) where relevant, and underpinned by appropriate computational resources, and;
 - c. Where possible, available as findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) builds and/or containers that can support self-deployment on local / institutional or independent computational infrastructures.
- B. Has expert support available to help install, optimise and/or containerise additional software tools and workflows, and policies for sustainable maintenance, updates and version control of these tools/workflows;
- C. Is easily connectable to suitable community data storage locations, including: public databases (e.g. the international proteomics data repositories (e.g. UniProt, ProteomeXchange); various data storage solutions including national, institutional or other data storage options; as well as the ability to upload and incorporate user-generated data;
- D. Has appropriate user authorisation and sharing mechanisms to allow for secure data sharing, solely at the discretion of a data owner/custodian;
- E. Includes user-friendly and community contributed and curated documentation, supported by experts in proteomics and computational infrastructure, and addressing aspects of the

¹⁶⁶ Subject to the results of a platform functionality comparison/gap analysis, scoping of compute requirements, agreement with various computational providers about hosting, and outcomes of further consultation with end use

¹⁶⁷ A selection of software tools, as listed in Appendix 1

¹⁶⁸ A selection of pipelines and / or workflows, as listed in Appendix 1, but also as identified by continued consultation with the community.

¹⁶⁹ Peak (Tier 1) high performance computing (HPC) is defined as a compute capability in the global top 200. Australia's Tier 1 facilities are the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) and Pawsey Supercomputing Centre. Examples of Tier 2 include state-level systems (e.g QRIScloud / QCIF) and institutionally operated facilities.

¹⁷⁰ Fit-for-purpose proteomics HPC and cloud resources to be determined in close consultation with the SIG and the Australasian Core Facilities group.

¹⁷¹ Galaxy Australia <https://usegalaxy.org.au/>

software tools, workflows and the shared platform, and;

F. Is connected to a data management component, described in D3.

D2. Interactive environments to enable secondary analyses, visualisation, and exploration of proteomics data, both raw and derived

To address objective 2 (i.e. to make it easier for Australian researchers to perform secondary analyses, visualisation and exploratory data analysis for raw (primary) and derived (secondary) proteomics data), it is proposed to implement / deploy:

- A. Hosted frameworks to enable researchers to utilise common packages for secondary analysis, visualisation, and exploratory data analysis, suitable for both raw and derived data (imaging, statistics, visualisation);
- B. Appropriate user authorisation and sharing mechanisms to allow for public or private data and associated data product(s) sharing, solely at the discretion of a data owner/custodian, and;
- C. Documentation on how to use the system (including a knowledgebase with community-contributed content) and the proteomics workflows on the system (connected to the community-curated documentation in D1-E).

D3. Systems to enable retrieval and submission of raw (primary) and derived (secondary) proteomics datasets from / to appropriate global repositories

To address objective 3 (i.e. to make it easier for researchers to publish high-quality reproducible proteomics data in accordance with best-practice open science guidelines, while accommodating the numerous different analysis types within proteomics) it is proposed to implement / deploy:

- A. Rapid data transfer between relevant national and international repositories and the shared proteomics platform (described in D1);
- B. An Australian 'staging post' for raw and derived proteomics data that is ready for public release via international repositories. The selected system should include formatting checks (i.e. validation) for data and metadata (enabled by a data management component), and;
- C. Documentation on how and when to use the D3 system (connected to the community-curated documentation in D1-E).

D4. A proteomics-specific bioinformatics training program, developed in conjunction with the proteomics community

To address objective 4 (i.e. to describe and coordinate a bioinformatics training program that will support the proteomics community to use data, software tools and workflows) it is proposed to implement / deploy comprehensive training resources for the described deliverables that;

- A. Make it easier for any Australian researcher to gain expertise in proteomics bioinformatics tools, workflows and infrastructure options (described in D1-D3).

D5. Alignment, adoption and contribution to global best-practice efforts

To address objective 5 (i.e. to address objectives D1-D4 in the context of international proteomics efforts, aligning, adopting and collaborating where possible) it is proposed to;

- A. Support and / or establish, and maintain, forums that allow information exchange and collaboration between the Australian and international proteomics communities; and
- B. Where possible actively participate and integrate Australian efforts with international efforts.

4.4 Implementation Timeframes

It is intended that the components identified in Section 4.3 will be implemented throughout the latter half of 2022 and in 2023 / 2024.

As of December 2022, several key activities that are relevant to the proposed infrastructure are already underway:

Component	Planned dates for delivery	Notes
D1- Aa/Ab. Key software tools ¹⁷² and workflows ¹⁷³ for data conversion, processing, quality control, identification, quantitation, post-processing (pathway analysis, multi-omics) and other analyses (imaging, statistics, visualisation).	On-going	Researchers can easily identify which proteomics analysis tools (and versions thereof) are currently installed as modules across several national, state and institutional infrastructures, including Pawsey, NCI, QRIScloud/UQ-RCC, and Galaxy Australia, as well as finding links to downloadable software containers for installation anywhere through the searchable interactive webpage the BioCommons ToolFinder ¹⁷⁴ .

¹⁷² A selection of software tools, as listed in [Appendix 1](#)

¹⁷³ A selection of pipelines and / or workflows, as listed in [Appendix 1](#), but also as identified by continued consultation with the community.

¹⁷⁴ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/tool-finder>

		<p>Tool installation request mechanisms on these systems are also highlighted through the ToolFinder.</p> <p>Workflows being developed as part of the BioCommons are registered on WorkflowHub¹⁷⁵, and those tested on Australian computational infrastructures by the BioCommons 'BYOD' Expansion Project¹⁷⁶ are highlighted in the dedicated Australian BioCommons space on WorkflowHub¹⁷⁷.</p> <p>An Australasian Core Facilities (ACF)-BioCommons working group has been established (Q1 2022) to identify priority tools and workflows for the proteomics community in Australia.</p>
D1-Aa. Key tools installed (dependencies included) on suitable command line interface (CLI) analysis environments (tier 1 and 2 ¹⁷⁸ HPC).	On-going	<p>As of December 2022, four of the tools listed in Appendix 1 (MaxQuant, Python, R, and RStudio) are installed as modules on QRIScloud / UQ-RCC HPC machines and three of the tools (R, JupyterNotebook and python) are available at NCI (either as modules or through Open On Demand¹⁷⁹).</p> <p>Installation of further software tools to support proteomics analysis as modules (or containers) across NCI, Pawsey, and QRIScloud/UQ-RCC infrastructures is being undertaken as part of the BioCommons 'BYOD' Expansion Project.</p> <p>An Australasian Core Facilities (ACF)-BioCommons working group has been established (Q1 2022 onwards) to identify priority tools and workflows for installation on CLI environments suitable for the proteomics community in Australia.</p>
D1-Aa. CLI platform	Ongoing	BioCommons partner infrastructures at NCI,

¹⁷⁵ <https://workflowhub.eu/>

¹⁷⁶ BioCommons 'Bring Your Own Data' Expansion Project <https://www.biocommons.org.au/byod-expansion>

¹⁷⁷ <https://workflowhub.eu/programmes/8/workflows>

¹⁷⁸ Peak (Tier 1) high performance computing (HPC) is defined as a compute capability in the global top 200. Australia's Tier 1 facilities are the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) and Pawsey Supercomputing Centre. Examples of Tier 2 include state-level systems (e.g QRIScloud / QCIF) and institutionally operated facilities.

¹⁷⁹ <https://opus.nci.org.au/display/OOD>

<p>appropriately resourced for performing proteomics analyses</p>		<p>Pawsey, and QCIF include computational systems that are capable of performing any part of a proteomics analysis.</p> <p>Enabling increased researcher access to partner HPC systems via mechanisms other than through the National Computational Merit Allocation Scheme (NCMAS)¹⁸⁰ or partner shares are under active development by NCI (Adapter scheme¹⁸¹) and through the Australian BioCommons Leadership Share (ABLeS) which has been established to support the collaborative generation of reference datasets of national importance.</p>
<p>D1-Ab. Where relevant, installed and optimised on graphical user interface (GUI) cloud based analysis platforms (e.g. Galaxy Australia¹⁸²)</p>	<p>Ongoing</p>	<p>As of December 2022, 5 of the tools listed in Appendix 1 were available via Galaxy Australia:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cardinal ● FlashLFQ ● MaxQuant ● Morpheus ● OpenMS <p>LFQanalyst¹⁸³ is currently being wrapped for use in the Galaxy platform and subsequent installation onto Galaxy Australia as part of the Australian BioCommons BYOD project.</p> <p>Tool installations can be requested by any member of the community for Galaxy Australia¹⁸⁴ at any time.</p> <p>An Australasian Core Facilities (ACF)-BioCommons working group was established in Q1 2022, and will identify priority tools for installation on Galaxy Australia, and develop standardised off-the-shelf workflows for the Australian proteomics community.</p> <p>We propose that these efforts will feed into a specialised / focussed proteomics analysis flavour of Galaxy Australia that should be established in early 2023 (e.g.</p>

¹⁸⁰ <https://my.nci.org.au/mancini/ncmas/2021/>

¹⁸¹ <https://nci.org.au/users/how-access-nci/adapter-scheme>

¹⁸² Galaxy Australia <https://usegalaxy.org.au/>

¹⁸³ Shah A.D. *et al.* 2020, <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jproteome.9b00496>

¹⁸⁴ <https://request.usegalaxy.org.au/>

		proteomics.usegalaxy.org.au), that includes only proteomics analysis relevant tools and a more pertinent central panel that is presented upon arrival.
D1-Ab. Galaxy Australia appropriately resourced for performing proteomics analyses	Ongoing	As of November 2022, Galaxy Australia is underpinned by a total of 2285 vCPUs and 24 TB RAM, including one 2 TB and four 4 TB high memory nodes that are reserved for specific tools requiring high memory. Access to the high memory nodes can be configured for specific proteomics analysis tools if and when required.
D1-Ac. Tools and workflows available as findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) builds and/or containers that can support self-deployment on local / institutional or independent computational infrastructures.	On-going	The Australian BioCommons, through the BioCommons 'BYOD' Expansion Project , is investigating methods to make builds and containers findable (ToolFinder) and deployable, via integration with conda, biocontainers and registries like bio.tools ¹⁸⁵ and WorkflowHub ¹⁸⁶ / Dockstore ¹⁸⁷ , but also through domestic container management approaches.
D1-B. Has support available to support installation, optimisation and/or containerisation of requested additional software tools and workflows, and sustainable policies for maintenance, updates and version control of these tools / workflows.	On-going	Researchers can directly request software installation on the computational systems mentioned in ToolFinder : please see the 'Requesting tool installations' section links provided for more information.
D1-C. Connectable to Nationally available storage	On-going	Streamlined connectivity of storage to Pawsey, QCIF, NCI, and other computational resources may be implemented in the BioCommons 'BYOD' Expansion Project .
D1-D/D2-B. Has appropriate user authorisation and sharing mechanisms to allow for data	Ongoing	AAF is currently engaged by the BioCommons to explore Access and Authentication Frameworks that will be fit for purpose across all envisaged BioCommons-related platforms and services. Technical solution options for future deployment

¹⁸⁵ Ison, J. *et al.* 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkv1116> & <https://bio.tools/>

¹⁸⁶ Goble, C. *et al.* 2021, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4605653> & <https://workflowhub.eu/>

¹⁸⁷ Yuen D., Cabansay L. *et al.* 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab346> & <https://dockstore.org/>

sharing, solely at the discretion of a data owner/custodian.		include CILogon ¹⁸⁸ .
D1-E/D2-C/D3-C. Includes a user-friendly and community curated documentation component, supported by experts in proteomics and computational infrastructure.	On-going	Support to researchers in the form of Frequently Asked Questions and documentation are available on the Australian BioCommons Support Pages ¹⁸⁹ . Further support and documentation are provided in the format of the ToolFinder , BioCommons Training Program ¹⁹⁰ and Galaxy Training Program ¹⁹¹ . The growth of technical documentation and support is ongoing and currently being explored in a number of formats beyond the current offerings in the BioCommons: including How-to-Guides ¹⁹² , documentation guidelines ¹⁹³ and through alignment with international registries for tools and workflows (e.g. bio.tools and WorkflowHub).
D2-A. Hosted frameworks to enable researchers to utilise common packages for secondary analysis, visualisation, and exploratory data analysis, suitable for both raw and derived data.	On-going	'Interactive environments' offered through the Galaxy Australia platform include RStudio and Jupyter notebooks are being trialled with planned implementation in 2022. The tool LFQanalyst, developed by Monash Proteomics, is currently being wrapped for Galaxy Australia.
D4. A comprehensive training resource for all components.	On-going	Introductory level training has occurred for software containerisation ¹⁹⁴ ; getting started with command line ¹⁹⁵ , Galaxy Australia ¹⁹⁶ , bio.tools/EDAM ¹⁹⁷ and R ¹⁹⁸ along with > 60 other webinar and workshop recordings. You can search the Australian BioCommons Training Materials Zenodo

¹⁸⁸ <https://www.cilogon.org/home>

¹⁸⁹ <http://support.biocommons.org.au/support/solutions>

¹⁹⁰ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/biocommons-training>

¹⁹¹ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/galaxy-au-training>

¹⁹² <https://australianbiocommons.github.io/how-to-guides/>

¹⁹³ <https://australianbiocommons.github.io/how-to-guides/documentation/DocumentationGuidelines.html>

¹⁹⁴ Workshop: Containers in Bioinformatics: Containerising a Pipeline, Building Containers and BYO Pipeline, delivered by Dr Marco de la Pierre <https://youtu.be/cQwi8slu5CM> <https://youtu.be/-e4nVO1vWrw> <https://youtu.be/RYnWTFJdZ-Y>

¹⁹⁵ Webinar: Getting Started with Command Line Bioinformatics, delivered by Parice Brandies

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5068996>

¹⁹⁶ Webinar: Galaxy Australia: a Strengthened National Life Science Platform that Engages Globally, delivered by Dr Gareth Price & Simon Gladman https://youtu.be/4W0Zal_8WiBU

¹⁹⁷ Webinar: bio.tools - making it easier to find, understand and cite biological tools and software, delivered by Hans Ienasescu & Matúš Kalaš <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6758146>

¹⁹⁸ Webinar: Getting Started with R, delivered by Dr Saskia Freytag <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5214276> & WORKSHOP: R: fundamental skills for biologists, delivered by Dr Saskia Freytag <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6766950>

		<p>Repository¹⁹⁹ for materials as well as the Australian BioCommons YouTube channel²⁰⁰ for recordings from many of these events.</p> <p>Further training material for proteomics can be located through international bioinformatics training repositories such as TeSS²⁰¹ or GOBLET²⁰², and the development and launch of the DReSA (Digital Research Skills Australasia)²⁰³ platform in November 2021 provides a further way of discovering digital research and training resources from a number of informatics training providers in Australasia.</p> <p>An Australasian Core Facilities (ACF)-BioCommons working group has been established (Q1 2022) and will identify and begin addressing training requirements for proteomics at the national level in association with the Australian BioCommons Training program²⁰⁴.</p>
<p>D5. Alignment, adoption and contribution to global best-practice efforts.</p>	<p>On-going</p>	<p>Through collaborations with ELIXIR, and others, the BioCommons is aligning with and adopting global best practice infrastructure solutions where possible. See the activities page on the BioCommons website²⁰⁵. Examples include the integration of the software discovery service ToolFinder with bio.tools and the EDAM ontology, the installation and optimisation of key proteomics tools on Galaxy (MaxQuant, LFQanalyst) and the set up and testing of an Australian NextFlow Tower service. In future, this will also include tailored alignments to international proteomics communities.</p>

¹⁹⁹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/australianbiocommons-training>

²⁰⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/australianbiocommons>

²⁰¹ Beard N., Bacall F. *et al.* 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btaa047> & <https://tess.elixir-europe.org/>

²⁰² <https://www.mygoblet.org/training-materials/>

²⁰³ <https://dresa.org.au/>

²⁰⁴ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/biocommons-training>

²⁰⁵ <https://www.biocommons.org.au/activities>

Appendix 1: open source tools for shared analysis environments

Proteomics tools for consideration for inclusion in a shared analysis environment. This list distils both the **tools** and **pipelines** requested for a shared platform as well as all the general tools used (+ **databases / platforms**): as identified by a survey of the Australian mass spectrometry community, and on-going consultations with the proteomics community in Australia.

Tool / pipeline / database / platform	High level description / Purpose	Download URL	Info / manual URL	Publication DOI
UniProt	Database: protein sequences + functional information	NA	https://www.uniprot.org/	https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gky1049
KEGG	Database: high level biological system functions	NA	https://www.genome.jp/kegg/	https://doi.org/10.1002/pro.3715
Galaxy Australia	Open, web-based platform for accessible, reproducible, and transparent computational biological research	NA	https://usegalaxy.org.au/	https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gka434
Trans Proteomic Pipeline (TPP)	Shotgun proteomics (MS/MS)	https://sourceforge.net/projects/sashimi/files/Trans-Proteomic%20Pipeline%20%28TPP%29/	http://tools.proteomecenter.org/software.php	https://doi.org/10.1002/prca.201400164
Cardinal	Analysis of mass spectrometry imaging (MSI) data	http://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/Cardinal.html	http://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/manuals/Cardinal/man/Cardinal.pdf	https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btv146
DIA-NN	Data processing for data-independent acquisition (DIA) proteomics	https://github.com/vdemichev/diann	https://github.com/vdemichev/diann#table-of-contents	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0638-x
FlashLFQ	Label free quantitation of peptides (tool also part of meta-morpheus)	https://github.com/smith-chem-wisc/FlashLFQ	https://github.com/smith-chem-wisc/FlashLFQ/wiki	https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jproteome.7b00608
Fragpipe	Wrapper (+GUI) for a complete MSFragger analysis workflow	https://github.com/Nesvilab/FragPipe	https://fragpipe.nesvilab.org/	https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jproteome.2c00390
Jupyter Notebook	Open source web application:	https://jupyter.org/install.html	https://jupyter.org/	https://eprints.soton.ac.uk/4039

	documentation and live codes / visualisation			13/
LFQAnalyst	Differential expression analysis for label-free quantitative proteomics (using MaxQuant outputs)	https://github.com/MonashBioinformaticsPlatform/LFQ-Analyst/#local-installation	https://bioinformatics.erc.monash.edu/apps/LFQ-Analyst/	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jproteome.9b00496
MaxQuant	Quantitative proteomics software for high resolution MS	https://www.maxquant.org/download_asset/maxquant/latest	https://www.maxquant.org/	https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt.1511
Morpheus	Matrix visualisation & analysis	https://github.com/cmaph/morpheus.js	https://software.broadinstitute.org/morpheus/documentation.html	https://doi.org/10.1021/pr301024c
MSFragger	Peptide ID search tool	https://github.com/Nesvilab/MSFragger/wiki/Preparing-MSFragger#Downloading-MSFragger	http://msfragger.nesvilab.org/	https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.4256
OpenMS	Open source data management / analysis for LC-MS	https://github.com/OpenMS/OpenMS/releases	https://www.openms.de/	https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.3959
Percolator	Semi-supervised learning: shotgun peptide ID	https://github.com/percolator/percolator/releases	http://percolator.ms/	https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth1113
Perseus	Statistical tools for omics data analysis	https://maxquant.net/download_asset/perseus/latest	https://maxquant.net/perseus/	https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.3901
pip / python	Python package installer & Python	https://anaconda.org/anaconda/pip	https://pip.pypa.io/en/stable/	https://pip.pypa.io/en/stable/
R	Programming language	https://mirror.aarnet.edu.au/pub/CRAN/	https://www.r-project.org/	R Core Team (2022) https://www.R-project.org
RStudio	Development environment	https://rstudio.com/products/rstudio/	https://rstudio.com/	RStudio Team (2020) http://www.rstudio.com/
Skyline	Open source client app, building quantitative methods: SRM, MRM, PRM, DIA/SWATH, DDA/MS1	https://skyline.ms/project/home/software/Skyline/begin.view	https://skyline.ms	https://dx.doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btq054

SwathXtend	Utilities for integrating SWATH spectral libraries with SWATH data	http://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/SwathXtend.html	http://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/SwathXtend.html	https://dx.doi.org/10.1074/mcp.M115.055558
XlinkProphet	Auto-validate XL-MS cleavable peptide cross links	http://brucelab.gs.washington.edu/software.html	http://brucelab.gs.washington.edu/software.html	https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty720

Appendix 2: proprietary tools for proteomics

Proprietary proteomics tools as identified through the survey of Australian mass spectrometry users, and on-going consultations with the proteomics community in Australia. This list distils both the **tools** and pipelines requested for a shared platform as well as all the general tools used (+ **databases / platforms**).

Tool / pipeline, database / platform	Company / Provider	High level description / Purpose	Info/manual URL
CLC Genomics Workbench	Qiagen	Next generation sequencing toolkit	https://digitalinsights.qiagen.com/products-overview/discovery-insights-portfolio/analysis-and-visualization/qiagen-clc-genomics-workbench/
Agilent MassHunter	Agilent	LC-MS and GC-MS software	https://www.agilent.com/en/promotions/masshunter-mass-spec
Biopharma Finder	ThermoFisher Scientific	Workflow toolkit for characterisation of biotherapeutics	https://www.thermofisher.com/au/en/home/industrial/mass-spectrometry/liquid-chromatography-mass-spectrometry-lc-ms/lc-ms-software/multi-omics-data-analysis/biopharma-finder-software.html
Byonic	Protein Metrics	Search engine for MS/MS	https://www.proteinmetrics.com/products/byonic/
Compound Discoverer	ThermoFisher Scientific	Small molecule identification software	https://www.thermofisher.com/au/en/home/industrial/mass-spectrometry/liquid-chromatography-mass-spectrometry-lc-ms/lc-ms-software/multi-omics-data-analysis/compound-discoverer-software.html
IPA	QIAGEN	Pathway mapping	https://www.qiagen.com/us/products/discovery-and-translational-research/next-generation-sequencing/informatics-and-data/interpretation-content-databases/ingenuity-pathway-analysis/

LipidSearch	ThermoFisher Scientific	Lipid identification for liquid-chromatography MS	https://www.thermofisher.com/order/catalog/product/IQLAAEGABSFAPCMBFK#/IQLAAEGABSFAPCMBFK
Mascot	MatrixScience	Database searches for MS/MS and peptide mass fingerprinting	https://www.matrixscience.com/
Mass Dynamics	Mass Dynamics	Software toolkit for protein discovery and characterisation	https://www.massdynamics.com/
Multiquant	SCIEX	MS data processing and quantitation software	https://sciex.com/products/software/multiquant-software
PEAKS	Bioinformatics Solutions Inc.	Software toolkit - see website for different versions	https://www.bioinfor.com/peaks-software/
PEAKS Studio X+	Bioinformatics Solutions Inc.	Identification, quantitation and visualisation for proteomics	https://www.bioinfor.com/peaks-studio/
PeakView	SCIEX	Review for MS data including LC-MS/MS and standalone MS/MS	https://sciex.com/products/software/peakview-software
Progenesis QI	Nonlinear Dynamics	Software for analysis of LC-MS experiments	https://www.nonlinear.com/progenesis/qi/
ProteinPilot	SCIEX	Software for identification and relative quantitation of proteins	https://sciex.com/products/software/proteinpilot-software
Proteome Discoverer	ThermoFisher Scientific	Software for identification and relative quantitation of proteins	https://www.thermofisher.com/order/catalog/product/OPTON-30812?SID=srch-srp-OPTON-30812
Scaffold	Proteome Software	Software for characterisation of MS/MS data from proteomics	http://www.proteomesoftware.com/products/scaffold/
SCIEX (cloud, OneOmics)	SCIEX	Cloud platform for multi-omics analysis, including SWATH	https://sciex.com/applications/life-science-research/oneomics
SCiLS Lab	SCiLS	MS imaging processing, statistics	https://scils.de/

		and visualisation	
Spectronaut	Biognosys	Software for DIA discovery based proteomics	https://biognosys.com/shop/spectronaut
TraceFinder	ThermoFisher Scientific	Software for HTS (high-throughput screening) and quantitation with chromatography-MS	https://www.thermofisher.com/au/en/home/industrial/mass-spectrometry/liquid-chromatography-mass-spectrometry-lc-ms/lc-ms-software/lc-ms-data-acquisition-software/tracefinder-software.html

Appendix 3: community survey questions

General

- How would you describe your level of experience with mass spectrometry analysis?
 - Very experienced
 - Some experience
 - Beginner
 - Interested but no direct experience
 - Other

- Which 'omics fields does your mass spectrometry work fall under?
 - Metabolomics
 - Meta-metabolomics
 - Proteomics
 - Meta-proteomics
 - Other

- Which broad application area(s) have you worked in, or will work in, during the next 5 years?
 - Human health / medical
 - Fundamental bio-research
 - Environmental
 - Agriculture
 - Food & beverage
 - Other

- Which sample type(s) have you worked on, or will work on in the next 5 years?
 - Fluids (e.g. blood, serum, urine)
 - Tissues (e.g. heart, liver, brain)
 - Micro-organisms (e.g. cultures, isolates)

- Environmental (soil)
 - Environmental (water)
 - Environmental (air)
 - Other
- Which process(es) do you / group members perform, or envisage performing in the next 5 years?
- Bioinformatics tool development (e.g. processing, inference, machine learning)
 - Bioinformatics tool implementation (e.g. MaxQuant for quantitative proteomics)
 - Data pre-processing and management
 - Gas chromatography - mass spectrometry
 - Liquid chromatography - mass spectrometry
 - Labelled quantitation (SILAC, iTRAQ)
 - Label-free quantitation (LFQ)
 - Mass spectrometry only (e.g. direct surface analysis, infusion)
 - Mass spectrometry assay development
 - Shot-gun peptide identification
 - Statistical analyses
 - Other

Tools and pipelines you use

- Which (if any) tools / software / pipelines / programs / platforms do you or group members use (choose all that apply)? Please only indicate those you'd currently recommend for use . **NB. this list is non-exhaustive so please note preferences not listed in 'other'
- Cardinal
 - DIA-Umpire
 - flashLFQ
 - Galaxy Australia
 - Jupyter Notebook
 - MaxQuant

- Morpheus
 - OpenMS tools
 - Percolator
 - Perseus
 - Proprietary tool(s)
 - Python
 - R / RStudio
 - Custom tool developed in our group or by collaborators
 - Other
- If you ticked the proprietary tools box above, what are they?
- Are there tools / software / pipelines / programs / platforms you'd like to use but that aren't suitable for your study taxon / project / sample? If so, what are they and why aren't they suitable?
- Are there tools / software / pipelines / programs / platforms you'd like to use but can't because of technical limitations (e.g. installation, compute requirements, dataset access requirements)? If so, what are the tools and what are the roadblocks you've encountered? What is your workaround and why is it inadequate?

Data you use

- What mass spectrometry platform/s are you currently using to generate data (choose all that apply)?
- FTICR
 - Q-Orbitrap-IonTrap
 - Q-Orbitrap
 - QqQ/QTRAP
 - Single Quadrupole
 - Ion Trap
 - ToF/ToF
 - Other

- Which of the following reference databases do you use (choose all that apply)? **NB. this list is non-exhaustive so please note preferences not listed in 'other'

 - Custom-made database
 - KEGG
 - PeptideAtlas
 - PRIDE
 - MassBank
 - MetaboLights
 - Metlin
 - UniProt
 - Other

Data management

- Do you use a data management tool and/or framework within your project(s)? If so, what?

- How do you share data within your group and with collaborators? Where are your collaborators based? What difficulties have you encountered?

- Do you make your datasets publicly available? Have you encountered any difficulties in doing so?

- If you answered yes above, which repositories do you use?
 - PeptideAtlas
 - PRIDE (EBI)
 - ProteomeXchange
 - MetaboLights (EBI)
 - Metabolomics Workbench (NIH)
 - Other

- If you don't make your datasets publicly available, why not?

- Commercial confidence issues
- I don't see a benefit in sharing my datasets
- I don't know how to make my datasets publicly available
- Other

Your compute infrastructure needs

- What kind of compute infrastructure setup do you use (choose all that apply)?
 - Local desktop/PC
 - High-performance computing within my research group
 - High-performance computing within my department
 - High-performance computing at my institution
 - High-performance computing at a collaborator's institution
 - High-performance computing at national or state level (e.g. NCI, Pawsey, QCIF/QRIScloud)
 - NeCTAR cloud instance
 - Commercial cloud (e.g. Amazon Web Services, Microsoft Azure, Google Cloud)
 - Galaxy
 - Other

- Do you have access to the expertise you need to build and maintain this compute infrastructure (e.g. installing and updating software)?
 - Yes, within our group
 - Yes, via collaborators
 - Yes, within our institution
 - Yes, via partner high-performance computing infrastructure (e.g. NCI, Pawsey, QCIF)
 - No, we would like to set some up or update our current approach but can't access expertise
 - Other

- Is your current compute infrastructure sufficient for your current needs? If not, why not?

- Will this compute infrastructure setup be sufficient for your needs in 2 years' time?
 - Yes, we expect to be doing mass spectrometry at a similar scale in 2 years' time
 - Yes, as we expect to be doing less mass spectrometry in 2 years' time
 - No, we expect to be doing more mass spectrometry by then and will need more resources
 - No, this infrastructure will be shut down or deprecated by then and we need to find a replacement
 - No, the responsible lab member will be moving on by then and we will need an alternative
 - I don't know
 - Other

- Will this compute infrastructure setup be sufficient for your needs in 5 years' time?
 - Yes, we expect to be doing mass spectrometry at a similar scale in 5 years' time
 - Yes, as we expect to be doing less mass spectrometry in 5 years' time
 - No, we expect to be doing more mass spectrometry by then and will need more resources
 - No, this infrastructure will be shut down or deprecated by then and we need to find a replacement
 - No, the responsible lab member will be moving on by then and we will need an alternative
 - I don't know
 - Other

Characteristics of a shared analysis platform

- Would you / group members use a shared compute infrastructure platform for bioinformatics?
 - Yes - we can't currently perform mass spectrometry without such a platform
 - Yes - our needs are currently met but we'd consider a shared platform if it was suitable
 - No - we will always prefer to perform our analyses locally no matter how good a shared platform is
 - Other

- How important are these general factors to you in a shared bioinformatics platform?
 - Following best practice in tools, formats and metadata; compliant with requirements of international data repositories
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant
 - Free (subsidised) to researchers no matter the scale of analysis
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant
 - Easy to access from anywhere
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant
 - Easy to self-manage access and permissions for collaborators
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant
 - Easy to upload/download data
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant
 - Security of data and analysis
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant
 - Long-term support for and sustainability of the platform
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant

- How important are these data-related factors to you in a shared bioinformatics platform?
 - Smart metadata handling (e.g. assistance with metadata formats, transfer of metadata through pipeline, controlled vocabulary lookup)
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant
 - Ability to submit datasets to international repositories from the platform
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant
 - Ability to download datasets from international repositories within the platform
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant
 - Ability to transfer data easily to/from storage
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant

- How important are these tool/pipeline-related factors to you in a shared bioinformatics platform?
 - Access to our preferred tools/pipelines
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant
 - Access to a choice of tools/pipelines
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant
 - Quick installation of other tools/pipelines upon request

- Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant
- Assistance available in implementing pipelines
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant

- What are the top 1-5 tools/pipelines you would absolutely require in a shared bioinformatics platform?

- How important are these compute-related factors to you in a shared bioinformatics platform?
 - Ability to scale up/down resources used as needed
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant
 - No need to understand or control the compute backend
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant
 - Compatibility with external analysis environments (e.g. Amazon, Cyverse)
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant

- How important are these training-related factors to you in a shared bioinformatics platform?
 - Good documentation on how to use the platform
 - Crucial
 - Important

- Unimportant
- Good documentation on how to use the tools/pipelines
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant
- Access to in-person training on how to use the platform
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant
- Access to in-person training on how to use the tools/pipelines
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant
- Discussion forum to share expertise with other users
 - Crucial
 - Important
 - Unimportant

- Are there any other factors you consider crucial in a shared bioinformatics platform? If so, what?

Is there anything else you'd like to tell us or suggest?

- Please let us know here.

Document Control

VERSION	DATE	AUTHOR(S)	DESCRIPTION
V 1.0	April 2022	Johan Gustafsson and Jeff Christiansen (Australian BioCommons)	First draft - intended for community comment by Proteomics SIG members and others (please add comments directly into the document). Subsequent iterations of the document will be produced following consultation with other stakeholder groups (i.e. international entities operating proteomics facilities / infrastructure elsewhere and)
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